

ISic0154

Epitaph of Clodia Thalia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 104

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. Clodia

2. Thalia

3. v(ixit) a(nnis) XX

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Clodia Thalia lived for 20 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285124
EDR 111300
EDCS 22100093

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7392 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 74
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